

Academic Procrastination Tendencies Among The Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) Student-Teachers

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Abstract

The Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) is one of the flagships of the National Education Policy 2020 and a dual degree course- education and another subject of choice. The current paper aims to study the prevalence of academic procrastination tendencies among the Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) student-teachers. This cross-sectional study looks into the difference of academic procrastination among the male and female ITEP student-teachers. Along with that, it also investigated the academic procrastination according to the year of study- 1st, 2nd and 3rd year. The study was conducted on 41 ITEP student-teachers studying in the Department of education, Rajiv Gandhi University, Arunachal Pradesh. For the purpose of data collection, descriptive survey design was employed and the Academic procrastination Scale by Gupta and Bashir was used and distributed through a google form. Statistical techniques like Mean, SD, frequency, percentage analysis, t-test and ANOVA were employed for data analysis. The findings showed that the ITEP student-teachers have moderate to low academic procrastination (91%). Male students procrastinate more than female, but statistically there is no significant difference at .05 level, $t(39) = 1.99$, $p=0.054$. 1st year students were the most procrastinating, followed by 3rd year and 2nd year students. The ANOVA result showed that year of study are not statistically significant $F(2, 15.20)=1.63$, $p=.227$.

Keywords

ITEP, NEP 2020, Academic Procrastination, RGU.

Introduction

Educating future educators is an essential task as they mould the next generation. In order to do this effectively, teacher training must combine different fields of study, personal values, and hands-on experience under expert mentors. Since this training requires a mix of deep subject knowledge and teaching skills, it should take place in broad, multidisciplinary institutions rather than isolated teaching schools. The primary path forward is a 4-year Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) envisioned in the National Education Policy (NEP), 2020. This program allows students to do a double major in both education and a specific subject of their choice, like History, Political Science, Hindi, Physics, Chemistry, Economics etc. (NEP, 2020; NCTE). The ultimate goal of the ITEP program is to produce high-quality, motivated teachers who have the expertise and values needed to create the best possible learning environment for students at every grade (Jabbar & Barkati, 2024).

Objective of study

The objectives of the study are:

1. To measure the level of Academic Procrastination among the ITEP student-teachers.
2. To identify whether there is any significant difference between the level of academic procrastination among the male and female ITEP student-teachers.
3. To find whether there is any significant difference between the level of academic procrastination among the 1st, 2nd & 3rd year ITEP student-teachers.

Review of Literature

Procrastination is defined as putting off a task or assignment. It is the inability to complete any activity within the intended time limit or deadline, despite knowing that it must be done, and they want to do it (Ackerman & Gloss, 2005). Similarly, Silver and Sabini (1981) also defined a procrastinator as someone who knows what to do and wants to do it yet is unable to do it, hence it is an irrational delay. It can be characterised as a behavioural tendency to defer and evade the completion of tasks or taking decisions (Balhara & Mittal, 2022). Wirajaya (2020) has listed different causes of academic procrastination that include lack of time management, lack of task aggressiveness, lack of sincerity, poor personal initiatives, fear of failure, high expectations of results, lack of motivation, excessive perfectionism, lack of focus, and uncertainty on how to begin the

task. Mustafa (2025), believes that procrastination is a complex, multifaceted phenomenon that is influenced by societal standards, technological distractions, emotional fragility, shortcomings of academic institutions, and inefficient individual actions. It is also caused by a rigid teaching style, unclear assignment specifications, delayed feedback, and lack of academic guidance. There is no single definition that encompasses the meaning of procrastination. It is a multi-dimensional issue that includes both cognitive and behavioral aspects (Balhara & Mittal, 2022). But it is evident that an increase in procrastination leads to a decrease in the quality of work (Steel et al, 2001). Approximately one in five adults experience procrastination (Harriott & Ferarri, 1996) and it is more common in academic settings (Ackerman & Gloss, 2005) known as Academic Procrastination. Academic Procrastination is a prevalent issue among university students (Day et al., 2000) and 52% pre-service teachers have high academic procrastination (Aponte, 2024). Addressing academic procrastination tendencies is an essential component of effective pre-service education (Gadatia, 2024). When a future teacher develops a habit of delaying their academic tasks, it compromises the quality of their training and leads to poor educational outcomes (Ataş Akdemir, 2019). Therefore, prioritizing research into academic procrastination is essential to uncover the specific ways it hinders a student's development and long-term success as better understanding of academic procrastination will help the pre-service teachers for their teaching (Irfan et al., 2024).

Rationale of the study

NEP 2020 requires the student-teachers of Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) to master multidisciplinary content and pedagogy. However, academic procrastination leads to substandard educational outcomes and compromises the professional values essential for future educators. This study specifically aims to measure the tendencies of academic procrastination among ITEP student-teachers to identify the prevalence of it in the rigorous curriculum. Without this data, it remains unclear how academic procrastination hinders the development of passionate and well-equipped teachers envisioned by the NCTE and NEP.

Research Questions

The research questions of the study are

1. What is the level of Academic Procrastination among the ITEP student-teachers?
2. Is there any significant difference between the level of academic procrastination among the male and female ITEP student-teachers?
3. Is there any significant difference between the level of academic procrastination among the 1st, 2nd & 3rd year ITEP student-teachers?

Methodology

The study used a descriptive cross-sectional survey design as it seeks to examine the prevalence of academic procrastination among ITEP student-teachers of Rajiv Gandhi University, Arunachal Pradesh, at a specific point in time and compare these levels across different demographic subgroups.

Study Group

The population of the study was the ITEP student-teachers enrolled in the Department of Education Rajiv Gandhi University, Arunachal Pradesh only. The ITEP course was started by the department in the year 2023 with an intake capacity of 50 students each year. Currently, there are three ongoing batches. The first batch of the program are now in their third year and additionally two batches have joined since. There are 46 students in 1st year, 34 in 2nd year and 8 students in the 3rd year totalling to 88 students. The sample consist of 41 students which included 30 female students (73%) and 11 male students (27%). In terms of their year of study, 1st year students 14, (34%), 2nd year students, 20 (49%), and 3rd year students, 7 (17%) are part of this research study.

Data collection

The data was collected with the help of google form which included the statements of the Academic procrastination Scale by Gupta and Bashir (2018). The google form recorded two variables i.e., Gender and Year of study that was necessary for this study. The 'Academic Procrastination scale' developed by Gupta and Bashir is composed of 30 statements. Out of that, 22 items were positive and 8 were negative. It follows a 5-point scale namely; Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. For the positive statements, the scoring was 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 while for negative statements it was reversed: 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5. It has a Cronbach alpha reliability of 0.76. Therefore, the scale was deemed reliable for the study.

Analysis

The data was analysed with the help of MS Excel and jamovi version-2.6. To address the objectives of the study, a combination of descriptive and inferential statistics was used. For objective 1, frequency and percentage analysis was used to determine the overall level of academic procrastination. To test the difference in male and female ITEP student-teachers, mean, standard deviation (SD), and t-test was conducted. Finally, a one-way ANOVA was utilised to compare the three groups of ITEP student-teachers (1st year, 2nd year and 3rd year).

Findings

Academic procrastination tendencies

In this section, the academic procrastination tendencies of the ITEP student-teachers are given. Table 1 shows how many students are in different levels of academic procrastination. It was found that the majority of the ITEP student-teachers have below average to moderate level of procrastination. Fig 1 shows the percentage analysis of procrastination where 42% are below average, 32% Moderate, 17% low while 7% are above average and only 2% exhibit high procrastination. Notably 0% falls under the extremely high and extremely low groups. It can be said that the ITEP student-teachers of Rajiv Gandhi University have moderate to low procrastination (91%).

Table 1. Level of Procrastination among the ITEP Student-teachers.

Procrastination Level	Number of Students
Extremely High	0
High	1
Above average	3
Moderate	13
Below Average	17
Low	7
Extremely Low	0
Total	41

Fig 1. Percentage analysis of procrastination level among ITEP student-teachers

Academic Procrastination by Gender

This section shows whether there is any significant difference between the academic procrastination of male and female ITEP student-teachers.

Table 2. Group Descriptive of the male and female ITEP student-teachers

	Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE
Procrastination	Male	11	86.7	85.0	13.8	4.15
	Female	30	78.7	77.5	10.5	1.91

Table 2 shows the number of male and female ITEP student-teachers. The male (n=11) has a mean of 86.7, SD=13.8. the female students (n=30) have a mean value of 78.7 and SD=10.5. The mean value of the male students is higher than female students, thus we can say that the male students procrastinate more than female students. In order to determine whether there is a significant difference between the academic procrastination of male and female students, t-test was done. Table 3 shows the result of the independent t-test. The difference was not statistically significant at .05 level, $t(39) = 1.99, p=0.054$. Hence the null hypothesis (H01) is accepted. There is no significant difference between the academic procrastination of male and female students.

Table 3. Independent t-test result of male and female students

		Statistic	df	p	Mean difference	SE difference	Effect Size

Procrastination	Student's t	1.99	39.00	0.054	7.99	4.02	Cohen's d	0.701
Note. $H_a \mu_{Male} \neq \mu_{Female}$								

Academic Procrastination by Year of Study

Table 4. Group descriptive of the ITEP student-teachers according to year of study

	Year of Study	N	Mean	SD	SE
Procrastination Level	1st Year	14	85.7	13.18	3.52
	2nd Year	20	78.0	9.99	2.23
	3rd Year	7	79.3	12.42	4.69

In this section, the academic procrastination of each year of study is discussed. Table 4 shows the group description of all three years of study. The 1st year students (n=14) have a Mean value of 85.7 and SD=13.18; 2nd year students (n=20) have a mean value of 78 and SD= 9.99 and 3rd year students have mean value= 79.3 and SD=12.42. From the table it can be said that the 1st year students procrastinate more than the 2nd and 3rd year students. The 3rd year students procrastinate more than 2nd year students. Hence, 1st year ITEP student-teachers procrastinates most in their academic tasks followed by the 3rd year students while 2nd year students have the least procrastination among them. In order to see whether there is any significant difference between them, One- way ANOVA test was conducted. Table 5 shows the ANOVA result, F (2,15.20=1.63, p=.227) which means they are not statistically significant. Hence, the null hypothesis (H02) is accepted. There is no significant difference between the academic procrastination of 1st, 2nd & 3rd year ITEP student-teachers.

Table 5. One-Way ANOVA (Welch's)

	F	df1	df2	p
Procrastination Level	1.63	2	15.2	0.227

Conclusion

The study shows that the ITEP student-teachers have moderate to low procrastination, a result that aligns with previous studies (Incecam et al., 2017; Özer & Yetkin, 2018; Ataş Akdemir, 2019; Caka, 2021.) Although Nova et al. (2025) reported high procrastination in different context, the variations observed by Gadatia (2024) confirms that academic procrastination levels are not uniform across all pre-service teachers groups. Ultimately the findings suggest that the ITEP student-teachers are not inclined towards Academic Procrastination. The result that male ITEP student-teaches have higher academic procrastination than female students is consistent with the findings of Balkis & Duru (2009), Pala (2011), Incecam et al. (2017), Efe & Efe (2018), Ataş Akdemir (2019), Nova (2025). In contrast, Aponte (2024), recorded higher procrastination among female students (69%) than male students. However, despite these descriptive differences, the statistical analysis indicates that there is no significant difference between the male and female academic procrastination aligning with previous studies by Özer & Yetkin (2018) and Eren & Yaliz Solmaz (2019). The analysis of academic procrastination levels across different year of study indicates a flow of 1st year ITEP student-teachers > 3rd year ITEP student-teachers > 2nd year ITEP student-teachers. It means that the 1st year students showed highest procrastination followed by 3rd year and 2nd year students. On the basis of the data, it was found that there is no significant difference between the academic procrastination of 1st, 2nd & 3rd year ITEP student-teachers. The findings remain consistent with the outcomes of Özer & Yetkin (2018); Eren & Yaliz Solmaz (2019) suggesting that overall impact of year of study remain statistically negligible.

Procrastination tendency can be effectively brought down with the help of various interventions like assigning and consistently monitoring homework, providing literary books, motivational advices (Naki, 2019). Further the availability of guidance and counselling facilities can play a crucial role in mitigating procrastination and improving student productivity (Efe & Efe, 2018). By promoting effective time management, regular study habits, providing academic assistance and encouraging a problem solving mindset (Irfan et al., 2024; Gadatia, 2024; Mustafa, 2025) can help institutions better equip to help in overcoming academic procrastination.

Limitation of the Study

This study is limited by its focus on a single institution, meaning the findings cannot be generalised to all ITEP student-teachers across different regions. To address this, future studies should incorporate a broader sample of students from across the state for more comprehensive results.

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